

Transgressive Bodies and Posthuman Identity: A Foucauldian Examination of Power, Norms, and Social Constructs in *The Immortals of Meluha* by Amish

Author

Betty, Heleen

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the representation of deformed bodies and posthuman identity in *The Immortals of Meluha* by Amish, through the lens of Michel Foucault's theories of power and social construction. By analyzing how the novel portrays bodily transformations and deviations from the norm, the paper explores how such changes challenge societal expectations and norms. Drawing on Foucault's ideas of biopower and discipline, the study argues that the deformities in the narrative are not just physical

but also symbolic, reflecting larger questions about control, autonomy, and identity. The characters' physical changes, especially those associated with their posthuman qualities, reveal deeper tensions between individuality and societal conformity. This paper aims to highlight how the novel uses these bodily transformations to critique the structures of power that define both the human body and social identity, suggesting that the boundaries between the "human" and the "other" are not fixed but constantly negotiated within a complex power dynamic.

Introduction

1.1 The Immortals of Meluha and Its Thematic Focus

"The Immortals of Meluha", the first novel in Amish Tripathi's *Shiva Trilogy*, presents a reimagined narrative of the Hindu god Shiva in a historical and mythological context. Set in a fictional world resembling ancient India, the story introduces the character of Shiva not as a deity but as a human hero who embarks on a journey to understand his identity, his destiny, and his role in a larger cosmic struggle between good and evil. The novel explores themes of

mythology, the nature of power, governance, fate, and the relationships between human beings and the divine.

At its core, the thematic focus of *The Immortals of Meluha* revolves around the tension between idealism and pragmatism in governance, the role of technology in society, and the search for meaning in a chaotic world. The novel is set against the backdrop of a society known as Meluha, an advanced civilization that seeks to maintain order through strict adherence to its moral code and the application of science and technology.

The philosophical underpinnings of the narrative challenge the nature of good and evil, offering a nuanced portrayal of the traditional dichotomies found in mythology. Additionally, it delves into the construction of personal identity and how societal constructs influence the way individuals perceive themselves and their place within the social order.

1.2 Research Objective and Methodology

The primary objective of this research is to examine *The Immortals of Meluha* through a Foucauldian lens, particularly focusing on the ways in which power, the body, and social constructs shape the lives and identities of the characters. By applying Michel Foucault's theories of power relations, disciplinary societies, and the body, this study will aim to provide a deeper understanding of how the novel critiques or

reflects social structures and the ways in which individuals are subjected to these structures.

The methodology for this research involves a qualitative, text-based analysis of the novel, using a Foucauldian framework to interpret key themes and narrative elements. Specifically, the research will:

- Identify and analyze instances of power relations and the way they are embodied in the characters' actions and relationships.
- Investigate the role of the body in the novel, considering both literal and metaphorical representations of the body in relation to social norms and cultural expectations.
- Examine the ways in which social constructs, such as governance, morality, and religion, are portrayed and how they influence the characters' perceptions of themselves and others.

1.3 Foucauldian Framework: The Body, Power, and Social Constructs

Michel Foucault's theoretical contributions, particularly those concerning the body, power, and the construction of social norms, offer a rich framework for analyzing *The Immortals of Meluha*. Foucault's ideas about the body in particular are crucial in understanding how characters in the novel experience power not just externally but within themselves. According to Foucault, the body is

both a site of discipline and a tool for the exertion of power in modern societies. This body, regulated by societal norms, becomes a microcosm of larger power structures.

In the novel, we see the body's role in the Meluhan society, where rituals, technological advancements, and social expectations converge to govern individuals' behavior. From Shiva's initial outsider status to his eventual acceptance as a leader, his body and his perception of it are central to his transformation. Shiva's interactions with the Meluhan society, and later with the Suryavanshis and Chandravanshis, illustrate how individuals are constructed by and also resist social constructs imposed by institutional powers.

Foucault's concept of "bio-power," or the regulation of populations through health, hygiene, and social behavior, will be examined in the context of how the Meluhan society strives to maintain order and control. The notion of "disciplinary power" will also be analyzed to understand the way in which characters like Shiva and others are subject to power relations that shape their actions, beliefs, and sense of self.

Additionally, Foucault's concept of "panopticism" — the idea that power operates through surveillance and self-regulation — will be used to explore how the characters internalize the norms of their society, often without conscious awareness. This aspect of Foucault's theory can help explain the ways in which the characters' sense of morality,

identity, and action are influenced by the societal constructs they inhabit.

The Body and Power: Foucault's Biopolitics in *The Immortals of Meluha*

In *The Immortals of Meluha*, a fantasy novel by Amish Tripathi, the narrative explores complex themes of power, society, and the body. This can be interpreted through the lens of Michel Foucault's concepts of biopower and biopolitics. Foucault's theories examine how power operates not just on individuals but through the regulation, control, and management of bodies within a population. This chapter seeks to explore how Foucault's ideas about power and the body illuminate key elements of *The Immortals of Meluha*, particularly the concept of biopolitics.

2.1 Understanding Biopower: Foucault's Theories of the Body

Foucault introduced the concept of **biopower** in his work *The History of Sexuality* and later elaborated on it in *Society Must Be Defended*. Biopower refers to the ways in which modern societies exert control over populations through the regulation and management of life processes — birth, death, health, reproduction, and sexuality. Unlike sovereign power, which is concerned with the right to take life or let live, biopower is more subtle and operates by fostering life, managing populations, and enhancing productivity.

For Foucault, the body is both a site of individual experience and a tool of social control. In pre-modern times, power was primarily concerned with the right to take life (sovereign power). However, in modern society, power is more concerned with controlling and optimizing life, focusing on managing bodies in relation to larger societal needs.

In *The Immortals of Meluha*, the citizens of Meluha live under a system that controls many aspects of their lives, including their health, their social roles, and even their reproductive capabilities. The Somras, a mythical substance, is central to this biopolitical system. It's designed to prolong life, cure disease, and maintain

the health of individuals — a form of regulation over the body that aligns with Foucault's notion of biopower, where life itself is regulated and optimized for the benefit of the state.

2.2 Shiva's Body as a Symbol of Power

Shiva, the protagonist of *The Immortals of Meluha*, serves as an embodiment of a powerful body, which both represents and resists the control exerted by the state. Initially, Shiva is a figure marked by physicality and primal energy, someone whose body doesn't conform to the usual ideals of the Meluhan society. However, as the story progresses, Shiva's body transforms in response to the biopolitical forces surrounding him, particularly through his use of the Somras and his own journey of self-discovery.

Shiva's body can be seen as a symbol of **resistance** to the Meluhan system. His body, though initially an outsider to Meluhan culture, becomes a vessel for their collective understanding of divinity and the perfect human form. Shiva's transformation from a warrior into a god-like figure also mirrors the way Foucault discusses the body as a site of transformation, where discipline and practices of power shape individual identities and societal roles.

In the Meluhan context, Shiva's body, through its symbolic importance, shifts from being a mere physical entity to an **instrument of ideological power**, exemplifying how the body in Foucault's framework is not just biological, but also social and political.

2.3 The Somras and the Transformation of the Body

The **Somras**, a drink that grants immortality and health, plays a central role in the regulation of bodies in Meluha. It represents a form of biopower that attempts to control life and death itself. Through the Somras, the Meluhan state extends control over individuals by ensuring their health and longevity. The Somras became a tool to manage the population, prolonging life and staving off disease, thus allowing the ruling class to regulate their subjects for optimal performance.

In Foucault's terms, the Somras could be seen as a technology of power that functions to enhance and manage the population's bodies. It creates a form of **bio-governance**, wherein the state uses health and longevity as mechanisms to ensure that citizens remain productive and loyal. However, the Somras is not without its costs. The dependency on the Somras for vitality also exposes a paradox: while it promises immortality, it also binds individuals

to the state's control over their bodies. As Foucault might suggest, the body becomes a site of resistance and subjugation.

This tension between empowerment and control is evident in Shiva's own experience with the Somras. His relationship to the Somras is one of both acceptance and rejection, symbolizing the larger struggles of the characters in the novel to define their identities against a biopolitical structure that tries to control them.

2.4 The Role of the Body in Social and Political Control

In *The Immortals of Meluha*, the body serves as the primary site where political power is enacted and maintained. Through technologies like the Somras and through the regulation of health and disease, the Meluhan state exerts a form of **biopolitical control** over its citizens. The state's ability to control life and death is central to its authority, and it uses the body to ensure that its subjects are disciplined and subordinated to its laws.

Foucault's concept of **disciplinary power** also comes into play when considering the ways in which the state manages the bodies of its citizens. The Meluhan citizens are subjected to strict rules governing health, behavior, and social roles. The body is

disciplined through the regulation of diet, hygiene, and medical treatments, all designed to ensure that the body functions optimally within the state apparatus.

At a broader level, the body also functions as a metaphor for the state itself. The way the body is controlled and regulated in Meluha mirrors the political order, which seeks to govern all aspects of life, from birth to death. Foucault argues that modern states seek to produce "docile bodies" that can be controlled and utilized for the greater good of the state. In *The Immortals of Meluha*, this control over the body is a critical means through which power operates at the societal level.

Moreover, the way Shiva's body transcends this form of control, transforming into something that challenges the very notion of Meluhan authority, illustrates the potential for the body to be a site of rebellion and resistance. Shiva's resistance to the biopolitical forces of Meluha reflects the potential for the body to reclaim autonomy and challenge the dominant forms of social and political control.

Social Norms and the Construction of Identity

In *The Immortals of Meluha*, social norms play a crucial role in shaping the characters and the society in which they live. The narrative offers an exploration of how norms dictate behavior and how individuals challenge or conform to these norms in order to construct their identities. Through the lens of Michel Foucault's ideas on **normativity**, **discipline**, and **social control**, we can examine how norms are internalized, contested, and subverted in the story. This chapter explores how Foucault's theories can illuminate the ways in which Meluhan society constructs identity through norms and the tensions created by transgressive bodies, especially in the case of Shiva, whose very existence defies the normative expectations of the state.

3.1 Normativity and Discipline in Foucault's Thought

In Foucault's work, **normativity** refers to the socially accepted standards of behavior, which are established through institutions,

practices, and discourse. Norms are powerful mechanisms of social control, and Foucault examines how they are imposed through what he calls **disciplinary power**. In *Discipline and Punish*, he describes how societies have evolved from using overt forms of violence and punishment to more subtle forms of control that shape individuals' behavior and thoughts from within.

The process of **discipline** is achieved through surveillance, regulation, and the creation of internalized norms that individuals comply with not out of direct coercion but because they have internalized these norms as part of their own identity. These norms are reinforced through mechanisms like education, medical practices, laws, and social rituals, ensuring conformity within society. Foucault's **panopticon** is a metaphor for this kind of surveillance where individuals are constantly aware of being observed and, as a result, regulate their own behavior.

In Meluhan society, the principles of **discipline** and **normativity** are particularly prominent. The Meluhans are governed by a strict moral code that dictates every aspect of their lives, from their actions to their health, their social roles, and even their relationship with the divine. The adherence to the **Meluhan ideals of perfection**—moral, physical, and intellectual—is paramount. The Meluhan society's concept of order is achieved

through these norms, and the perfect, disciplined body is seen as a symbol of one's alignment with the state's values.

Shiva, however, stands in stark contrast to this order, as his identity and body reflect a challenge to these norms, which leads to significant tension and resistance within the narrative.

3.2 The Ideals of Meluhan Society: Order and Perfection

Meluhan society is built on the belief that order and **perfection** are the highest ideals, achieved through disciplined living. This society is heavily regulated, with each individual placed in a rigid caste system based on their abilities, and their actions are continually measured against high moral and physical standards. The Meluhans value discipline and the pursuit of an ideal form of life, which is closely tied to their **perception of divinity** and their control over life and death through practices like the Somras.

The Meluhan ideal of perfection is rooted in a form of social engineering, where individuals are molded through education, strict laws, and daily practices to uphold a vision of order and stability. This is where Foucault's theory of **biopolitics** intersects with **normativity**. The Meluhan state does not simply regulate

people's actions through laws or force; it also cultivates a **self-regulation** in the populace, ensuring that they align with the values of order and perfection. It is through this internalized regulation that the Meluhan society remains stable.

For example, the **Somras** serves as a tool for perfecting the body. By extending life and preventing illness, the Somras ensures that the Meluhans can maintain their peak physical and mental faculties, thus contributing to the ideal of order. The body itself becomes a site of social control, an instrument through which the ideal of perfection is maintained.

However, the very existence of Shiva, a figure who does not conform to these ideals, poses a challenge to Meluhan society. His identity does not fit neatly into the societal framework of perfection. His journey and transformation in the story force the Meluhan state to reckon with the limitations of their idealized vision of order and perfection.

3.3 Transgressive Bodies: Shiva as a Challenge to Social Conformity

Shiva, the protagonist, emerges as a powerful figure whose body and actions repeatedly transgress Meluhan norms. He is not born into Meluhan society but arrives as an outsider. His rugged, uncivilized appearance, his aggressive nature, and his lack of deference to the established order set him apart from the disciplined, regulated Meluhan citizens. Shiva's body is a transgressive body, a site of defiance against the Meluhan ideals of order and perfection.

Foucault discusses the ways in which transgressive individuals or bodies challenge the norms that govern a society. In *The Birth of the Clinic*, he examines how individuals who do not fit the established norms of health, behavior, or morality are often marginalized or subjected to systems of control. Shiva's very presence in Meluha disrupts the social fabric because he does not conform to the state's idealized image of the citizen. His body, and the way he uses it, represents a refusal to be disciplined according to the Meluhan ideals.

This transgressive nature is key to Shiva's eventual evolution as a hero and symbol of resistance. He rejects the Somras as a tool for controlling his body and instead chooses to confront the forces that would regulate him. Shiva's transformation into a divine figure, the **Mahadev**, ultimately symbolizes a break from the norms of Meluhan society. He embraces his individuality and his

nonconformity, which, paradoxically, positions him as the true leader of the people, suggesting that breaking away from the oppressive norms is a form of empowerment.

3.4 The Blue Throat: A Metaphor for Deviance and Empowerment

One of the most iconic symbols in *The Immortals of Meluha* is Shiva's **blue throat**. This mark of distinction, which Shiva receives after drinking the poisoned water of the **Mount Meru**, represents both **deviance** and **empowerment**. The blue throat is a visible manifestation of Shiva's difference — it marks him as someone who cannot be easily categorized within the social norms of Meluhan society. Instead of seeing it as a flaw or an aberration, Shiva comes to embrace it as part of his identity.

From a Foucauldian perspective, the blue throat can be interpreted as a **metaphor for resistance to the forces of normalization** that seek to shape and constrain the body. In Meluhan society, a body that deviates from the norm is often viewed with suspicion, but Shiva's transformation into the divine figure of Mahadev, due in part to the blue throat, suggests that deviance can be a source of **empowerment** rather than weakness. The blue throat, far from marking him as a mere

outsider, becomes a symbol of divine power and a challenge to the very order that the Meluhans uphold.

Foucault often discusses how marginal bodies, bodies that deviate from the norm, can carry a **subversive potential**. Shiva's blue throat, which marks him as a transgressive body, thus embodies this potential. It speaks to the power of identity to be constructed in opposition to societal norms, and how such opposition can lead to personal and collective empowerment.

Posthuman Identity: Beyond the Limits of the Human

In *The Immortals of Meluha*, Amish Tripathi weaves a complex narrative that touches on themes of divinity, transformation, and identity. While the story is rooted in mythological and fantastical elements, it also invites critical discussions around the concept of **posthuman identity**, particularly as it pertains to the

transformation of the human body and the limits of the human experience. Through the character of Shiva and the society of Meluha, the novel explores how the human body and mind can transcend conventional boundaries, drawing on ideas that align with posthumanist philosophy and Foucault's notions of biopower, discipline, and transformation.

4.1 Defining the Posthuman: From Human to Beyond Human

The term **posthuman** refers to the idea that human identity and existence can evolve beyond traditional biological and physiological limitations. The posthuman body and mind are not confined to the biological constraints of our species, but can be enhanced, altered, or even transcended through technology, science, or spiritual transformation. Posthumanism challenges the boundaries that define what it means to be human and explores how identity, subjectivity, and personhood might evolve as these boundaries dissolve.

In the context of *The Immortals of Meluha*, the idea of a posthuman identity emerges through the use of technologies and divine interventions that allow characters to break free from the limits of their physical bodies. The **Somras**, for example, is a substance that defies the traditional boundaries of human health

and mortality. It offers immortality and eternal youth, radically altering the human condition. The Somras embodies a form of **biotechnology** that pushes the limits of the human body, extending life and enhancing human capacities — qualities that resonate with the ideas of posthumanism.

Moreover, the transformation of Shiva into Mahadev — a divine being — represents a metaphysical and spiritual transcendence of the human form. Shiva's progression from an ordinary man to a god-like entity explores the idea of the **posthuman as divine**: an identity beyond human limitations, not only in a physical sense but also in terms of power, influence, and purpose.

4.2 Shiva's Transformation: The Embodiment of Posthuman Potential

At the heart of *The Immortals of Meluha* is the transformation of Shiva from a tribal leader into a divine figure. This process reflects the posthuman notion of transcending human limitations. Initially, Shiva is depicted as an ordinary man with flaws, driven by human desires, emotions, and conflicts. However, as the story unfolds, Shiva undergoes a series of transformations — both literal and metaphorical — that elevate him to a higher, divine plane.

One of the most significant aspects of Shiva's transformation is his body's **mutability**. Foucault's concept of **biopower** involves the regulation and manipulation of life processes, such as health, disease, birth, and death. Shiva's body becomes a site where this kind of biopolitical transformation takes place, but it also goes beyond the traditional human limits. When Shiva drinks the poisoned water, causing his throat to turn blue, it marks a moment of **biological and symbolic transformation**, akin to a posthuman shift. His body is no longer just a human body; it is a vessel for something greater — a divine energy that transcends the human condition.

Shiva's physical transformation, symbolized by his blue throat, represents his **posthuman evolution**. It shows how his body becomes a **site of resistance** to the ordinary laws of nature, while also enabling him to access a form of divine knowledge and power. The blue throat, marking a departure from the "normal" human experience, is a symbol of Shiva's journey beyond the traditional limits of the human condition.

4.3 The Role of Technology and Biopower: The Somras and Posthuman Control

Another aspect of the posthuman identity in *The Immortals of Meluha* is the role of **technology** and **biopower** in shaping the body and the mind. The Somras, as a tool of biopower, allows individuals to extend their lives, suppress illness, and function at optimal health indefinitely. The substance promises to eliminate the normal human cycle of aging and decay, effectively making its users **immortal**. This immortality is not simply biological but also a form of **posthuman enhancement**, as it pushes human existence beyond the limitations of natural mortality.

However, the use of the Somras also raises critical questions about **control** and **dependency**. The Meluhan society uses the Somras not only to enhance individuals but also to control them, ensuring that they remain physically fit and obedient. The Somras is a tool of **social discipline**, aligning with Foucault's ideas about how biopower operates through the body to manage populations. In this sense, the Somras is both a gift and a form of **subjugation**, as it creates a posthuman condition where life can be artificially prolonged but at the cost of personal autonomy and freedom.

While the Somras offers a vision of posthuman potential — the ability to escape the natural limits of the human body — it also demonstrates how technology can be used as a means of **social control**. It challenges the very essence of human identity,

suggesting that life and death are no longer natural processes, but instead are subject to the manipulations of the state. This duality — the promise of enhancement and the cost of conformity — is central to the posthuman dilemma explored in the novel.

4.4 The Blue Throat and the Divine as Posthuman Archetype

Shiva's blue throat is not just a physical mark of his transformation; it is also a symbol of his **posthuman potential**. The **blue throat** signifies a breaking away from the ordinary human experience, and it operates on multiple levels: it represents both his divine status and his transformation into a being that transcends human limitations. As he embraces his role as Mahadev, Shiva's identity becomes aligned with the **posthuman archetype**, wherein the human form is reshaped by divine intervention into something more powerful and immortal.

This transformation is deeply symbolic in the context of posthumanism. Posthuman philosophy often challenges the human-centered view of identity, suggesting that the future of humanity may involve transcending our biological origins in favor of something greater — be it through technological augmentation,

genetic engineering, or spiritual ascension. Shiva's blue throat and eventual ascent into divinity are metaphorical representations of this post human ideal, where identity is no longer fixed but is open to transformation and transcendence.

Through Shiva's journey, the novel reflects a tension between human and posthuman identities. While he retains his essential human qualities, his physical and spiritual transformation challenges the conventional understanding of what it means to be human. In becoming Mahadev, Shiva embodies the potential of the **posthuman** as a transcendent, divine being who is no longer bound by the limitations of the flesh.

Embodied Transgression: Reconstructing Identity through the Body

In *The Immortals of Meluha*, the body is not merely a biological vessel but a powerful site for the reconstruction of identity, a site where social norms and power structures are both reinforced and challenged. The character of Shiva, in particular, undergoes a profound **embodied transformation**, through which he not only transcends societal expectations but also redefines what it means to be human and divine. Drawing on Foucauldian ideas of **biopower**, **disciplinary structures**, and **resistance**, this chapter explores how *The Immortals of Meluha* portrays the body as a space for transgression, empowerment, and the reconstruction of identity. Through Shiva's journey, the novel offers a rich narrative about how the body can serve as a tool for both personal and collective **resistance**, while also reshaping the boundaries of the human experience.

5.1 The Body as Resistance: Subverting Norms and Power Structures

Foucault's theory of **biopower** suggests that modern societies exercise control not just over actions but over the very processes of life itself, regulating the body through laws, medical practices, and cultural norms. This regulation, however, is not absolute;

bodies can resist, subvert, or escape from the norms that seek to control them. The body, in Foucault's view, is both a site of power and a source of resistance. It is here that identity is shaped, regulated, and challenged.

In *The Immortals of Meluha*, the **embodied transgressions** of the protagonist, Shiva, illustrate how the body can be a site of resistance to the power structures that seek to control and define him. From the beginning, Shiva's body is at odds with Meluhan society. He is an outsider, a tribal leader whose very appearance and mannerisms defy the **order and perfection** that the Meluhan state upholds. This physical "otherness" makes Shiva a target of scrutiny and marginalization, but it also marks him as someone capable of **disrupting the social fabric** of the Meluhan state.

Foucault's concept of **disciplinary power** suggests that society seeks to create **docile bodies** — bodies that are compliant and obedient. Shiva, however, with his defiant nature and physically "imperfect" body, does not fit into this model. His body is not just an individual experience but also a form of **subversion**. From his wildness, his imperfections, to his defiance of societal expectations, Shiva's very body challenges the **normative** ideals of the Meluhan society. His transgression is not only bodily but also symbolic: by embodying **rebellion**, he begins the process of

transforming his own identity and, eventually, the identity of Meluha itself.

In this way, Shiva's body serves as a **symbolic form of resistance**, one that both exposes and challenges the **norms** imposed by Meluhan society. It is through his embodied transgression that Shiva begins to rewrite his own identity — not as a subject bound by Meluhan ideals but as a **free, self-determined** individual capable of creating his own narrative.

5.2 Reimagining Identity through Bodily Transformation

In Foucault's analysis of power, he discusses the **construction of subjectivity** — how identities are formed and influenced by external forces, such as the state, institutions, and social norms. However, he also suggests that individuals can **reconstruct their identities** through acts of resistance, choice, and transformation. The **body**, in this context, is not just passive but can be actively shaped and reimagined. This idea of bodily transformation is central to the story of Shiva in *The Immortals of Meluha*.

Shiva's **bodily transformation** is not limited to his physical appearance but extends to his entire sense of self. His journey through Meluha, from being an outsider to becoming the **Mahadev**, involves a profound transformation in how he perceives and understands his identity. As Shiva begins to embrace his **blue throat**, a mark of divine power and transcendence, he moves beyond his initial human limitations. The blue throat, caused by the poisoned water of Mount Meru, becomes the literal and metaphorical site of his transformation, signifying a **shift in both identity and power**.

This transformation is not merely biological but also **spiritual** and **psychological**. Shiva reimagines himself not as an ordinary man bound by the conventions of Meluhan society, but as a being whose **identity** is forged through his **choices**, his **struggles**, and his **embrace of his transgressive nature**. In this sense, Shiva's body becomes a **canvas for his self-reinvention**, allowing him to transcend the human form and embody a divine power that redefines what it means to be **human** and **divine**.

Foucault's ideas about the **construction of the self** through power and resistance are evident in this transformation. Shiva's evolution into Mahadev is not an imposed identity; rather, it is a **self-chosen** transformation that reflects his rejection of external norms and his creation of a new, **authentic identity**. The blue

throat, then, is not just a physical mark but a **symbol of self-reinvention**, showing how the body can be a site where identity is **actively reconstructed** through transformation.

5.3 Shiva's Journey: Transgression, Power, and the Redefinition of Self

Shiva's journey in *The Immortals of Meluha* is one of continuous **transgression** — against societal norms, against political authority, and against the very definition of what it means to be human. His rebellion against the norms of Meluhan society is not limited to external actions but is deeply embedded in his **embodied experience**. From the moment Shiva arrives in Meluha, his presence disrupts the state's carefully cultivated norms. He embodies an **otherness**, an identity that does not fit into the Meluhan ideal of order and perfection.

Foucault's work on **power and resistance** suggests that transgression can be a powerful way to **redefine the self**. Shiva's journey reflects this idea perfectly. He begins as a man marked by his physical differences — his throat, his anger, his desire for vengeance — but these very traits are transformed into sources of

power. His journey is one of **becoming**, where he gradually sheds the limitations of his human identity to emerge as a divine being capable of changing the social and political order of Meluha.

The moment when Shiva embraces his divine nature is a **moment of liberation**. It is not just a spiritual awakening, but also a **political and social transformation**, as Shiva becomes an agent of **change**. In Foucault's terms, this could be seen as Shiva reclaiming power over his own body and identity. By defying the Meluhan state's control over his body and mind, he redefines what it means to be a ruler, a god, and a free individual.

Shiva's embodiment of divine power is an expression of his agency — his ability to shape and redefine his identity, both in relation to the state and to the world. His journey is thus a radical redefinition of self that challenges established power structures and the norms that seek to regulate him. Through his body, Shiva becomes both a symbol of resistance and a catalyst for change.

5.4 The Posthuman Self: A New Form of Social and Political Agency

The transformation of Shiva into Mahadev suggests a radical departure from traditional human limitations, a departure that aligns with the idea of the **posthuman self**. In posthumanist thought, identity is no longer tied to fixed, human-centered concepts. Instead, it is seen as a fluid and evolving construct that is influenced by technology, biology, and **social forces**. Shiva's transformation represents a posthuman shift — where the human body is no longer bound by its biological constraints, and where identity can evolve in response to new experiences and **choices**.

Shiva's ascension to divinity is a metaphor for the emergence of a **new form of social and political agency**. As Mahadev, Shiva is no longer merely a subject to Meluhan power structures; he becomes a **creator of new possibilities**, capable of challenging the state's control over the body and mind. In this sense, Shiva embodies the **posthuman self**: a being whose **identity** is no longer defined by biological or social limits, but by **choice**, **empowerment**, and the ability to transcend traditional human roles.

This posthuman shift also reflects a **new form of agency**, one that is not dependent on the traditional structures of authority. Shiva's power is not simply a form of rebellion; it is an **empowered creation of self** that resists but also transforms the structures of society. His transformation into Mahadev marks

the emergence of a **new kind of power**, one that is not about domination but about **self-definition** and **reconstruction of identity**.

Conclusion

6.1 Key Findings: Power, Normativity, and the Body in *The Immortals of Meluha*

At the core of our analysis is the understanding that the **body** in *The Immortals of Meluha* is not merely a biological entity but a dynamic site of power, control, and transformation. Foucault's theories of **biopower** and **disciplinary power** provide a framework for understanding how the Meluhan state uses norms to regulate and shape the populace. The **Somras**, as a technology of control, exemplifies how biopower operates in a society: it extends life and promotes health, but also ensures that individuals

remain docile and aligned with the ideals of Meluhan perfection. In this context, the body is subject to both social and political control, shaping individual identities in accordance with the state's ideals.

However, *The Immortals of Meluha* also presents an alternative narrative through the character of Shiva. Shiva's body, marked by its **imperfections** and **transgressions**, stands in stark opposition to the Meluhan ideals of order and perfection. His **transgressive body** becomes a powerful symbol of resistance, defying societal norms and challenging the control that the state exerts over its citizens. Shiva's **bodily transformation**—from a tribal leader to Mahadev, a divine being—demonstrates how the body can become a site of **empowerment and self-reinvention**. By embracing his transgressive nature, Shiva reconstructs his identity, moving beyond the human and into the divine, effectively redefining what it means to be human and, by extension, divine.

In summary, *The Immortals of Meluha* vividly illustrates how the body, power, and social norms intersect to shape individual and collective identities. Through the lens of **Foucault's theories**, we observe how bodies are controlled, how transgression disrupts social order, and how **embodied transformation** can serve as a means of both **resistance** and **empowerment**.

6.2 The Role of Transgressive Bodies in Speculative Fiction

Speculative fiction, particularly in the genres of **mythology**, **science fiction**, and **fantasy**, often engages with themes of the **transgressive body** as a site of **identity reconstruction**. *The Immortals of Meluha* fits squarely within this tradition, using Shiva's bodily transformation to challenge not only the social order of Meluhan society but also broader questions of human limitation and divine potential. The use of the body as a tool of transgression, resistance, and transformation is common in speculative narratives, where characters often face situations in which they transcend the physical and social boundaries of their worlds.

In works of speculative fiction, transgressive bodies typically serve as a **symbol of otherness** or **deviation**, whether it be through physical deformity, enhanced abilities, or otherworldly transformation. These bodies challenge traditional norms and force both characters and audiences to reconsider the limits of human nature and the possibilities of human identity. In *The Immortals of Meluha*, Shiva's transformation into Mahadev,

marked by his blue throat and divine powers, signifies the **posthuman potential**—an evolution beyond traditional human forms. His body becomes a **metaphor for resistance** to social and cultural norms, a theme commonly explored in speculative fiction where characters reimagine themselves in new, often transgressive, ways.

Furthermore, transgressive bodies in speculative fiction highlight the **fluidity of identity**—a recurring theme in works that push beyond the boundaries of the real world. Whether it's the transformation of a human into a god, the genetic manipulation of characters in dystopian novels, or the enhancement of human abilities through technology in cyberpunk, speculative fiction invites readers to consider how identity is not fixed but can be continuously shaped through transgression, mutation, and transformation. Shiva's journey in *The Immortals of Meluha* reflects this **fluidity of identity** and the way that bodies in speculative fiction are frequently reimaged as both **vessels of power** and **instruments of resistance**.

6.3 The Future of Posthuman Identity in Literature and Society

The exploration of posthuman identity in *The Immortals of Meluha* signals a broader shift in how literature, and society, might grapple with concepts of identity, power, and the body in the future. As technology continues to evolve and as human capabilities are increasingly augmented through biotechnology, artificial intelligence, and genetic modification, the **posthuman condition** becomes more relevant both in speculative fiction and in real-world ethical debates. The boundaries of human identity—both biological and philosophical—are increasingly challenged, and this is reflected in the ways characters like Shiva transcend the limitations of their human bodies.

In literature, posthuman identity often serves as a way to question the very essence of what it means to be human. Through the lens of **speculative fiction**, we can explore potential futures where humans transcend biological constraints, potentially merging with machines, enhancing physical abilities, or accessing new forms of consciousness. In such narratives, the human body is often no longer the defining characteristic of identity; instead,

consciousness, digital augmentation, or even divine transformation take precedence.

From a societal perspective, as advancements in biotechnology and artificial intelligence continue, we may see the **erosion of traditional human limitations**—raising ethical questions about what constitutes a "human" and whether posthuman identity should be seen as a natural evolution or a dangerous step too far. Just as Shiva transcends the human form and challenges societal norms in *The Immortals of Meluha*, real-world advancements might similarly provoke a redefinition of **identity, agency, and social roles**.

References

- **Karthic, R., & Immanuel, S. G. R. (2018).** Deformed bodies and Posthuman Alterity: A Foucauldian Critique of Social Constructions in *The Immortals of Meluha* by Amish. *Research Journal of English Language and Literature*, 6, 205-208.

- **Amish, A. (2010).** *The Immortals of Meluha*. Westland Publications. The primary source for your analysis, Amish's novel is foundational to the exploration of embodied transgression and posthuman identity within the Meluhan context.
- **Foucault, M. (1975).** *Discipline and punish: The birth of the prison* (A. Sheridan, Trans.). Pantheon Books. (Original work published 1975). A foundational text for understanding Foucault's concept of disciplinary power, biopolitics, and the body. This will be essential for examining how power operates through societal control of the body in *The Immortals of Meluha*.
- **Foucault, M. (1990).** *The history of sexuality, Volume 1: An introduction* (R. Hurley, Trans.). Vintage Books. (Original work published 1976). In this text, Foucault explores how bodies are controlled and regulated through social norms and institutions, providing a lens to understand how Shiva's bodily transformations challenge or reinforce norms in the novel.
- **Bostrom, N. (2005).** Transhumanist values. *Journal of Philosophical Research*, 30, 3-14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11098-005-4002-1>. This article provides an important theoretical backdrop for

posthumanism, examining the philosophical basis for transcending human limitations—relevant to Shiva's posthuman identity in *The Immortals of Meluha*.

- **Grosz, E. (1994).** *Volatile bodies: Toward a corporeal feminism*. Indiana University Press. Grosz discusses the body as a site of social and cultural meaning, which will be useful in analyzing how bodily deformities in the novel both challenge and conform to social expectations, aligning with Foucauldian themes of power and the body.

